

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		6		8

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: TrustworthinessParticular.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	-35.1937231
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	-23.1937231
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	-22.9821362
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	6.81476620
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	.81476620

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: TrustworthinessParticular.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	16.993	815.396	<.001
Patient	1	17.250	8754.775	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: TrustworthinessParticular.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Doctor	5.474	.192	16.993	28.555	<.001	5.069	5.878
Patient	6.022	.064	17.250	93.567	<.001	5.887	6.158

a. Dependent Variable: TrustworthinessParticular.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.286	.030	9.657	<.001	.233
	Var(2)	.005	.000	9.618	<.001	.004
	Corr(2,1)	.006	.073	.079	.937	-.137
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.661	.227	2.912	.004	.337
	Var(2)	.045	.025	1.832	.067	.016
	Corr(2,1)	-.131	.325	-.401	.688	-.653

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.350
	Var(2)	.006
	Corr(2,1)	.149
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	1.295
	Var(2)	.132
	Corr(2,1)	.476

a. Dependent Variable: TrustworthinessParticular.

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Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: BenevolenceParticular.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	105.904436
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	117.904436
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	118.116023
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	147.912925
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	141.912925

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: BenevolenceParticular.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	16.990	998.960	<.001
Patient	1	18.636	12102.472	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: BenevolenceParticular.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Doctor	5.825	.184	16.990	31.606	<.001	5.436	6.214
Patient	6.155	.056	18.636	110.011	<.001	6.038	6.272

a. Dependent Variable: BenevolenceParticular.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ... Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.356	.037	9.713	<.001	.291
	Var(2)	.009	.001	9.618	<.001	.007
	Corr(2,1)	.048	.073	.654	.513	-.096
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.611	.210	2.910	.004	.311
	Var(2)	.022	.017	1.265	.206	.005
	Corr(2,1)	.215	.422	.509	.611	-.571

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.436
	Var(2)	.010
	Corr(2,1)	.189
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	1.197
	Var(2)	.102
	Corr(2,1)	.795

a. Dependent Variable: BenevolenceParticular.

Mixed Model Analysis

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Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
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Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: IntegrityParticular.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	15.34102793
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	27.34102793
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	27.55261483
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	57.34951720
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	51.34951720

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: IntegrityParticular.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	16.996	817.639	<.001
Patient	1	15.454	5595.826	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: IntegrityParticular.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Doctor	5.966	.209	16.996	28.594	<.001	5.526	6.406
Patient	5.948	.080	15.454	74.805	<.001	5.779	6.117

a. Dependent Variable: IntegrityParticular.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.359	.037	9.577	<.001	.293
	Var(2)	.005	.000	9.618	<.001	.004
	Corr(2,1)	.004	.074	.052	.959	-.140
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.783	.269	2.913	.004	.400
	Var(2)	.077	.040	1.905	.057	.027
	Corr(2,1)	-.398	.273	-1.461	.144	-.784

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.441
	Var(2)	.006
	Corr(2,1)	.147
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	1.535
	Var(2)	.215
	Corr(2,1)	.210

a. Dependent Variable: IntegrityParticular.

Mixed Model Analysis

[DataSet1] /Users/atom/Library/Mobile Documents/com~apple~CloudDocs/Desktop/PhD Docs/Main study/OWM_1.2.sav

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
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Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		6		8

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: CompetenceParticular.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	-90.3350822
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	-78.3350822
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	-78.1234953
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	-48.3265930
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	-54.3265930

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: CompetenceParticular.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	16.998	412.075	<.001
Patient	1	18.877	8352.586	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: CompetenceParticular.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.718	.232	16.998	20.300	<.001	4.227	5.208
Patient	6.007	.066	18.877	91.392	<.001	5.869	6.144

a. Dependent Variable: CompetenceParticular.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.362	.037	9.696	<.001	.296
	Var(2)	.003	.000	9.618	<.001	.002
	Corr(2,1)	-.025	.073	-.343	.731	-.167
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.972	.333	2.914	.004	.496
	Var(2)	.041	.024	1.700	.089	.013
	Corr(2,1)	.061	.355	.172	.864	-.563

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter	95% ...	
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.443
	Var(2)	.003
	Corr(2,1)	.118
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	1.904
	Var(2)	.130
	Corr(2,1)	.641

a. Dependent Variable: CompetenceParticular.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		6		8

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	657.470113
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	669.470113
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	669.681700
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	699.478603
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	693.478603

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	16.195	2313.967	<.001
Patient	1	17.815	7131.318	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Doctor	3.911	.081	16.195	48.104	<.001	3.738	4.083
Patient	4.102	.049	17.815	84.447	<.001	4.000	4.204

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.192	.020	9.676	<.001	.157
	Var(2)	.383	.040	9.617	<.001	.312
	Corr(2,1)	.171	.071	2.397	.017	.029
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.079	.041	1.929	.054	.029
	Var(2)	.023	.014	1.681	.093	.007
	Corr(2,1)	.137	.388	.352	.725	-.564

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter	95% ...	
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.236
	Var(2)	.469
	Corr(2,1)	.306
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.219
	Var(2)	.074
	Corr(2,1)	.723

a. Dependent Variable: Trust.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		6		8

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Communication.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	465.524353
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	477.524353
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	477.735940
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	507.532842
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	501.532842

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Communication.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	17.017	1566.528	<.001
Patient	1	16.030	7606.586	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Communication.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.154	.105	17.017	39.579	<.001	3.933	4.376
Patient	4.376	.050	16.030	87.216	<.001	4.269	4.482

a. Dependent Variable: Communication.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.233	.024	9.643	<.001	.190
	Var(2)	.121	.013	9.618	<.001	.099
	Corr(2,1)	.384	.063	6.125	<.001	.255
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.185	.068	2.725	.006	.090
	Var(2)	.022	.015	1.443	.149	.006
	Corr(2,1)	.058	.359	.161	.872	-.571

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ...
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.285
	Var(2)	.148
	Corr(2,1)	.499
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.380
	Var(2)	.086
	Corr(2,1)	.644

a. Dependent Variable: Communication.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

		Number of Levels	Covariance Structure	Number of Parameters
Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		6		8

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	774.686374
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	786.686374
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	786.897961
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	816.694863
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	810.694863

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	16.130	1219.483	<.001
Patient	1	16.233	7023.370	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.092	.117	16.130	34.921	<.001	3.844	4.341
Patient	4.619	.055	16.233	83.806	<.001	4.502	4.736

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.358	.037	9.667	<.001	.292
	Var(2)	.363	.038	9.602	<.001	.296
	Corr(2,1)	.216	.070	3.076	.002	.075
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.208	.087	2.398	.016	.092
	Var(2)	.020	.018	1.129	.259	.004
	Corr(2,1)	.414	.415	.999	.318	-.493

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		95% ... Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.438
	Var(2)	.445
	Corr(2,1)	.348
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.471
	Var(2)	.114
	Corr(2,1)	.890

a. Dependent Variable: Satisfaction.

Mixed Model Analysis

Model Dimension^a

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Fixed Effects	Doctor	1		1
	Patient	1		1
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
Total		6		8

Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	795.037915
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	807.037915
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	807.249502
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	837.046404
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	831.046404

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	19.064	2988.741	<.001
Patient	1	13.483	7587.938	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Doctor	4.207	.077	19.064	54.669	<.001	4.046	4.368
Patient	4.674	.054	13.483	87.109	<.001	4.559	4.790

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.290	.030	9.576	<.001	.236
	Var(2)	.604	.062	9.718	<.001	.493
	Corr(2,1)	.375	.063	5.952	<.001	.245
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.047	.032	1.446	.148	.012
	Var(2)	.023	.019	1.217	.224	.005
	Corr(2,1)	.356	.461	.773	.439	-.579

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter	95% ...	
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.356
	Var(2)	.738
	Corr(2,1)	.491
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.182
	Var(2)	.116
	Corr(2,1)	.887

a. Dependent Variable: Relationship.

Mixed Model Analysis

Warnings

The final Hessian matrix is not positive definite although all convergence criteria are satisfied. The MIXED procedure continues despite this warning. Validity of subsequent results cannot be ascertained.

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Repeated Effects	Role	2	Unstructured Correlations	3
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Model Dimension^a

		Subject Variables	Number of Subjects
Fixed Effects	Doctor		
	Patient		
Random Effects	Doctor + Patient	D_ID	
Repeated Effects	Role	D_ID * Dyad_ID	203
Total			

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Information Criteria^a

-2 Restricted Log Likelihood	893.396832
Akaike's Information Criterion (AIC)	905.396832
Hurvich and Tsai's Criterion (AICC)	905.608418
Bozdogan's Criterion (CAIC)	935.405321
Schwarz's Bayesian Criterion (BIC)	929.405321

The information criteria are displayed in smaller-is-better form.

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Fixed Effects

Type III Tests of Fixed Effects^a

Source	Numerator df	Denominator df	F	Sig.
Doctor	1	18.141	2766.535	<.001
Patient	1	2.499	5000.075	<.001

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Estimates of Fixed Effects^a

Parameter	Estimate	Std. Error	df	t	Sig.	95% Confidence Interval	
						Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Doctor	3.827	.073	18.141	52.598	<.001	3.674	3.980
Patient	4.637	.066	2.499	70.711	<.001	4.403	4.872

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

Covariance Parameters

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter		Estimate	Std. Error	Wald Z	Sig.	95% ...
						Lower Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.326	.034	9.471	<.001	.265
	Var(2)	.824	.083	9.879	<.001	.676
	Corr(2,1)	.255	.069	3.714	<.001	.116
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.020	.031	.663	.507	.001
	Var(2)	.044	.031	1.411	.158	.011
	Corr(2,1)	1.000 ^b	.000	.	.	.

Estimates of Covariance Parameters^a

Parameter	95% ...	
		Upper Bound
Repeated Measures	Var(1)	.401
	Var(2)	1.005
	Corr(2,1)	.384
Doctor + Patient [subject = D_ID]	Var(1)	.389
	Var(2)	.178
	Corr(2,1)	.

a. Dependent Variable: Involvement.

b. This covariance parameter is redundant. The test statistic and confidence interval cannot be computed.